

NUTRI•KNOW

Farmer's
Encyclopedia
on innovative
Nutrient
Management
Solutions

EIP-AGRI
Operational Group
FERTICOOP

FERTICOOP

Evaluation of biogas produced in manure storage systems

Activities

- Installation of flexible cover to an existent pond for biogas production.
- Evaluation of the influent and the effluent of slurry.
- Determination of anaerobic biodegradability and methanization potential of the slurry.
- Evaluation of the produced biogas.

Further details

€ **Total budget:** € 178.959,58
Total financed: € 55.173,58 (EU);
€ 73.137,06 (DARP)

Main funding source: Rural development 2014-2020 for Operational Groups

Rural Development

Programme:

2014ES06RDRP009 Spain - Rural Development Programme (Regional) - Catalunya

🕒 Ended, 2022

📍 Catalunya, Spain

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Objectives

- Promote biogas production for its thermal valorization at the boiler of the farm.
- Reduce GHG and ammonia emissions through fertilizing optimization and adoption of manure management methodologies.
- Carry out exhaustive monitoring of a slurry pond with flexible cover as slurry storage system.
- Characterization of the slurry and the biogas.

Biogas production

Results

- Produced biogas showed high content of methane, but also high concentration of hydrogen sulphide that must be removed for the correct boiler operation.
- The composition of the biogas shows an average of 592.645 ppm of CH₄, that increases or decreases depending on the temperature: the most elevated temperatures, the more methane production.
- Biodegradability of the slurry also depends on temperature. The samples show a biodegradability of 12% at November and 78% at May.
- Emissions from digested slurry storage in uncovered ponds are higher than the non-treated slurry. When the ponds are covered, the reduction of the emissions is around 50%.

Context

The new legislation “Real Decret 153/2019” about fertilization and manure management establish new obligations on manure management, what implies a huge change on actual manure management methodologies. On the other hand, the Best Available Techniques (BAT) are protocols and rules that will condition fertilization and manure management.

Location in the Nutri-Know value chain

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These BATs are proceedings planned to apply on farm to reduce emissions. However, government has planned a flexible system of actuations to perform whenever these has as aim objective and can prove an emissions reduction. These BATs cover all steps and processes from livestock farming to manure application in lands and aim to optimize organic fertilizer, with a consequent ammonia emissions reduction.

Cooperatives are key stakeholders for the manure management following the government strategies of decentralization of manure: cooperatives can store manure from its farmer partners and treat it in small scale.

This project will represent different scenarios from different cooperatives: climate conditions, crops, kind and amount of slurry, distance from livestock farm to fertilized lands, kind of slurry transport and presence of manure treatment at livestock farm.

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Learn more about the project at www.nutri-know.eu

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